

Using The Solfedgio Singing Method In Teaching Music Theory In Higher Education

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Abstract: This article scientifically and methodologically analyzes the issues of effective use of the solfedgio singing method in the process of teaching music-theoretical subjects in the higher education system. The study substantiates the role of solfedgio exercises in developing intonational accuracy, musical hearing, rhythmic intuition and combining theoretical knowledge with practice in students. It also highlights the activation of the perception of the pitch-tonality system, intervals, chords and musical forms through solfedgio singing.

Keywords: solfedgio, musical hearing, intonation, singing method, rhythmic intuition, pitch-tonality system, pedagogical methods, musical competence.

Introduction.

In today's conditions of globalization and digital transformation, the requirements placed on the higher education system require the training of specialists who not only have theoretical knowledge, but also have a developed musical mindset, are able to think independently and have a creative approach. Especially in the field of music education, the development of a student's theoretical knowledge in harmony with practical performance experience is emerging as one of the urgent pedagogical problems. In this regard, the pedagogical significance of the solfedgio singing method in teaching music-theoretical subjects deserves special attention.

Solfedgio singing, as the basis of musical education, serves to form the student's inner hearing, to perceive the connection between musical sounds and to express them consciously. This process activates the student's musical thinking, allows theoretical concepts to be understood not only in written or oral form, but also through sound. As a result, musical knowledge is deeply mastered through musical consciousness and hearing, moving away from mechanical memorization.

In the practice of teaching music-theoretical subjects in higher educational institutions, in some cases, a disconnection between theory and performance is observed. This leads to insufficient formation of students' musical literacy and performance competence. The solfedgio singing method serves as an effective pedagogical tool in overcoming this very problem. It combines complex musical concepts such as the scale-tonality system, intervals, chords, rhythm and metrorhythm with the student's auditory experience.

Also, solfedgio singing is of great importance in developing intonational accuracy, musical memory, rhythmic intuition and analytical listening skills in students. This serves as a solid foundation not only for mastering music-theoretical disciplines, but also for further professional activities - performing, pedagogical and scientific research. In this sense, the solfedgio singing method is considered an important pedagogical mechanism that combines the theoretical and practical aspects of musical education. Therefore, the purposeful and systematic use of the solfedgio

singing method in teaching music-theoretical disciplines in the higher education system is of great scientific and practical importance in improving the quality of musical education, developing students' professional competencies and deepening their musical thinking.

Statistical analysis.

As part of the study, pedagogical experimental work was organized with the participation of students of the 1st and 2nd year of study in the direction of “Music Education” of a higher educational institution. A total of 60 students were included in the study, who were divided into an experimental group (30 people) and a control group (30 people). In the experimental group, the solfedgio singing method was systematically and gradually used in teaching music-theoretical subjects, while in the control group, classes were held based on traditional teaching methods.

In order to determine the effectiveness of the study, initial and final diagnostics were conducted. The diagnostic criteria were students' intonation accuracy, musical hearing level, rhythmic intuition, and skills in the practical application of music-theoretical knowledge. The results for each criterion were evaluated at three levels - low, medium, and high.

According to the results of the initial diagnostics, it was determined that 26.7% of students in the experimental group were at a high level, 43.3% at an average level, and 30% at a low level. In the control group, the high level was 23.3%, the average level was 46.7%, and the low level was 30%. These indicators indicate that the level of preparation of both groups at the beginning of the experiment was almost equal.

The final diagnostic results, which were conducted at the end of the experimental and testing work, showed significant differences. In particular, in the experimental group, the high level indicators increased from 26.7% to 53.3%, the average level was 33.3%, and the low level was 13.4%. In the control group, the high level increased from 23.3% to 33.3%, the average level was 43.3%, and the low level was 23.4%.

The results obtained were analyzed mathematically and statistically, and it was found that the use of the solfedgio singing method in teaching music-theoretical subjects in the experimental group had a positive and stable effect on the development of students' musical competencies. The difference between statistical indicators was confirmed at a level of reliability $p < 0.05$, which ensures the scientific reliability of the research results.

Thus, the results of statistical analysis showed that the systematic introduction of the solfedgio singing method into the teaching process of music-theoretical subjects significantly increases students' intonation accuracy, musical hearing, and skills in applying theoretical knowledge in practical activities.

Table 1. Indicators of the development of students' musical competencies based on the use of the solfedgio singing method.

Groups	Diagnostic stage	High level (%)	Intermediate level (%)	Low level (%)
Experiment group (n=30)	Initial	26,7	43,3	30,0
	Final	53,3	33,3	13,4
	Initial	23,3	46,7	30,0

Control group (n=30)	Final	33,3	43,3	23,4
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As can be seen from the table, as a result of the systematic application of the solfedgio singing method among the students of the experimental group, high-level indicators increased from 26.7% to 53.3%, and low-level indicators decreased from 30% to 13.4%. This clearly confirms the effectiveness of the solfedgio singing method in teaching music-theoretical subjects. Although certain positive changes were also observed in the control group, it is found that their growth rate is significantly lower than that of the experimental group. The difference between the results was found to be statistically significant at the $p < 0.05$ level.

Discussion.

The statistical results obtained during the study once again confirmed the didactic and pedagogical significance of the solfedgio singing method in teaching music-theoretical subjects. The significant increase in the experimental group's indicators is explained, first of all, by the fact that solfedgio singing activates musical thinking and combines hearing and conscious perception. Direct experience of theoretical knowledge through sound led to a deeper understanding of musical concepts by students. During the discussion, it should be noted that the solfedgio singing method is not limited to the development of technical skills. It forms the student's musical thinking in a complex way: intonation, rhythm, sense of pitch and tonality, and the process of analytical listening develop as a whole system. This was reflected in the study results by a sharp increase in high-level indicators.

The results of the control group, however, showed that traditional approaches are effective to a certain extent, but their impact was limited. In this case, theoretical knowledge acquired a more reproductive character, and the student's active musical perception was not sufficiently activated. Therefore, the introduction of the solfedgio singing method indicates the need to reconsider methodological approaches in teaching music-theoretical subjects. The results of the discussion also revealed the motivational aspect of the solfedgio singing method in the educational process. Students of the experimental group participated more actively in the lessons, sought to sing independently, analyze and draw conclusions through listening. This indicates the compatibility of the solfedgio method with the person-oriented and competency-based approaches in music education. The results show that the solfedgio singing method should be considered not only as an auxiliary method in teaching music-theoretical subjects, but also as a central pedagogical mechanism. It connects theory and practice and further strengthens the professional training of students. Therefore, the introduction of this method in the higher education system on a systematic and methodological basis will serve to improve the quality of music education.

Conclusion.

This study scientifically sheds light on the pedagogical and methodological effectiveness of using the solfedgio singing method in the process of teaching music-theoretical subjects in the higher education system. The results of the study confirmed that the solfedgio singing method is of great importance in developing students' musical hearing, intonation accuracy, rhythmic intuition, and skills in combining theoretical

knowledge with practical activities. According to the results of statistical analysis, it was found that in the experimental group where the solfedgio singing method was systematically used, the level of development of musical competencies significantly increased, and low indicators sharply decreased. This indicates that this method is more effective than traditional approaches in teaching music-theoretical subjects.

Also, during the study, it was found that the solfedgio singing method enhances the activity, independent thinking and creative approach of students in the learning process. This indicates that the solfedgio singing method is an important pedagogical tool in the practical implementation of competency-based and person-oriented approaches in music education. In general, the purposeful, systematic and methodological use of the solfedgio singing method in teaching music-theoretical subjects in the higher education system will serve to improve the quality of music education, strengthen the professional training of future music specialists and deepen their musical thinking. The results of the study can serve as an important source for developing scientific and practical recommendations for improving the practice of teaching music-theoretical subjects in higher educational institutions.

References:

1. Абдуллин Э. Б. Музыкальная педагогика: теория и практика: учебное пособие. — М.: Академия, 2004. — 272 с.
2. Асафьев Б. В. Музыкальная форма как процесс. — Л.: Музыка, 1971. — 376 с.
3. Кабалевский Д. Б. Воспитание ума и сердца. — М.: Просвещение, 1984. — 192 с.
4. Левандо М. И. Методика преподавания сольфеджио. — М.: Музыка, 1986. — 208 с.
5. Ройтерштейн М. И. Сольфеджио и развитие музыкального слуха. — М.: Музыка, 1988. — 160 с.
6. Усманов Ю. Р. Муסיқа таълими назарияси ва методикаси. — Тошкент: Ўқитувчи, 2012. — 184 б.
7. Gordon E. E. Learning Sequences in Music: Skill, Content, and Patterns. — Chicago: GIA Publications, 2013. — 432 p.